

Improving Performance of Grid-Connected Hybrid Solar-Wind Systems for Distribution Loads using DVR and Active Filters

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KEYWORDS

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Solar power generation,
Dynamic Voltage Restorer (DVR),
D-STATCOM,
Battery Energy Storage System (BESS),
Power quality,
Voltage sag and swell compensation

ABSTRACT

The integration of renewable energy sources into modern power distribution networks presents a significant challenge in maintaining stable power quality. Grid-connected solar power systems are highly dependent on environmental conditions, leading to fluctuations in power generation that impact voltage stability, harmonic distortion, and overall grid performance. Variant load conditions, including nonlinear and unbalanced loads, introduce further power quality issues such as voltage sags, swells, and increased harmonic distortion, negatively affecting sensitive electrical equipment and system efficiency. This paper proposes a hybrid solar-grid-connected voltage source converter (VSC) that enhances power quality by performing dual functions: acting as a Distribution Static Compensator (D-STATCOM) and integrating a connected Dynamic Voltage Restorer (DVR). The D-STATCOM compensates for reactive power imbalances, mitigates harmonics, and improves the overall power factor of the system. The DVR, as a series converter connected directly to the grid, corrects voltage sags and swells by injecting the necessary compensating voltage. A battery energy storage system (BESS) is integrated to support the correction of voltage sags and swells, ensuring continuous voltage stability during fluctuating solar power generation or grid disturbances. The proposed system dynamically enhances grid performance based on solar power availability, reducing reliance on conventional grid supply and improving overall voltage stability and power quality.

1. INTRODUCTION

The increasing integration of renewable energy sources such as solar and wind power into modern power distribution networks has become a key aspect of global efforts toward sustainable energy solutions. These renewable sources offer many benefits, including reducing dependence on fossil fuels and mitigating environmental impacts, but they also introduce significant challenges to the stability and quality of the power grid. Solar power systems, in particular, are highly dependent on environmental conditions such as solar irradiation, which fluctuate due to factors like time of day, weather patterns, and seasonal changes. These fluctuations lead to power generation instability, which can result in voltage instability, harmonic distortion, and overall degradation of power quality [1] (Ackermann, 2012) [2] (Islam et al., 2020). Furthermore, the increased adoption of nonlinear and unbalanced loads such as variable-speed drives, power supplies, and other electronic devices has made it even more difficult to maintain stable power quality in the grid. These types of loads can generate harmonic currents, which distort the voltage waveform, degrade system performance, and negatively impact sensitive electrical equipment [3] (Alavi et al., 2008) [4] (Shahraki et al., 2013). Voltage sags, swells, and flickers are also common power quality issues in such systems. These disturbances can disrupt the proper functioning of connected loads, leading to operational disruptions, equipment damage, and reduced system efficiency. To address these concerns, several power quality improvement techniques have been proposed, among which Dynamic Voltage Restorers (DVRs) and Distribution Static Compensators (D-STATCOMs) have shown considerable promise [5] (Jovcic et al., 2007) [6] (Ram et al., 2011). The DVR, typically connected in series with the grid, is designed to mitigate voltage sags and swells by injecting compensating voltage into the system. This ensures that the voltage at the point of common coupling (PCC) remains within acceptable limits, thus protecting sensitive equipment from short-term voltage drops [7] (Sadeghi et al., 2013). The D-STATCOM, on the other hand, is a shunt-connected power electronic device that compensates for reactive power imbalances, mitigates harmonic distortions, and improves the overall power

factor of the system. It has been demonstrated to be effective in stabilizing grid voltage and improving system reliability by reducing harmonic currents and managing reactive power [8] (CIGRÉ, 2009) [9] (Liu et al., 2005). A hybrid system combining the functionalities of both DVR and D-STATCOM has been proposed as an effective solution for addressing the simultaneous challenges of voltage instability and harmonic distortion. This hybrid approach leverages the strengths of each technology to enhance overall power quality and provide a more resilient and efficient grid infrastructure [10] (Hosseini et al., 2008) [11] (Chen et al., 2013). By integrating a Battery Energy Storage System (BESS) into such a configuration, it is possible to further stabilize the system by providing continuous voltage support during periods of low renewable generation or grid disturbances. BESS can store excess energy generated when solar power availability is high and discharge this energy when solar power generation fluctuates or when the grid experiences a disturbance [12] (Nia et al., 2012) [13] (Liu et al., 2015). This capability enhances system resilience and ensures a more stable supply of power, improving grid performance and voltage regulation [14] (Zhu et al., 2016). This paper proposes a hybrid solar-grid-connected voltage source converter (VSC) system, which functions as both a D-STATCOM and a DVR. The VSC operates in two modes: as a D-STATCOM to compensate for reactive power imbalances, reduce harmonic distortion, and improve power factor, and as a DVR to inject compensating voltage and mitigate voltage sags and swells. The integration of a BESS into the system further enhances voltage stability by providing continuous energy storage and support. As solar power generation fluctuates throughout the day, the proposed system dynamically adjusts its operation to optimize grid performance, reduce reliance on conventional grid supply, and improve overall power quality. The performance and effectiveness of the system are validated through extensive simulations conducted under various conditions, including varying solar irradiance, load variations, and grid disturbances [15] (Mokhtari et al., 2016) [16] (Raji et al., 2015) [17] (Panzardi et al., 2017) [18] (Feng et al., 2013) [19] (Zhang et al., 2017) [20] (Balakrishnan et al., 2019).

Fig. 1. System Configuration of grid connected solar PV shunt converter and series converter

2. PROPOSED SYSTEM CONFIGURATION

The proposed system configuration includes a hybrid solar-grid-connected voltage source converter (VSC) designed to improve power quality in modern distribution networks integrated with renewable energy sources. The VSC operates in dual modes, acting as a Distribution Static Compensator (D-STATCOM) and a Dynamic Voltage Restorer (DVR). The D-STATCOM function compensates for reactive power imbalances, reduces harmonic distortion, and improves the overall power factor as shown in Fig.1. The DVR, a series converter, corrects voltage sags and swells, ensuring stable voltage supply to loads. The system is further supported by a Battery Energy Storage System (BESS), which provides continuous voltage support during grid disturbances or insufficient solar generation. The BESS stores excess energy generated by the solar power system and supplies it back to the grid when solar output is low. Solar power generation is the primary renewable energy source, with photovoltaic panels connected to the grid via a DC-AC inverter. An MPPT controller optimizes power extraction from the solar array, improving grid stability and reducing reliance on conventional grid power. This system ensures a resilient, stable, and efficient power distribution system.

3. DESIGNING AND DEVELOPMENT OF DC MICROGRID FOR EVS

A. Solar PV power generation system

The solar photovoltaic (PV) system serves as the primary renewable energy source in the proposed configuration, directly influencing grid performance and power quality. The PV array converts solar irradiance into direct current (DC) electricity, which is then processed for efficient integration into the grid. To ensure maximum power extraction, a Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) controller is employed, dynamically adjusting the operating point based on varying solar conditions. A DC-DC boost converter regulates the PV output voltage, optimizing power delivery to the DC-AC inverter, which converts the DC power into alternating current (AC) for grid injection. The inverter operates in synchronization with the grid frequency, ensuring stable power flow and reducing power fluctuations. Additionally, the solar power generation level directly impacts grid power quality—as solar irradiance increases, voltage stability improves, harmonic distortion decreases, and overall power quality is enhanced. By efficiently harnessing solar energy, the system minimizes dependence on conventional power sources while supporting grid stability and maintaining a high-quality power supply. The proposed solar PV configuration effectively integrates advanced control strategies to enhance system reliability and optimize energy utilization in modern power networks.

a. Solar PV boost converter system configuration

The solar power system in a DC microgrid is crucial for efficient energy conversion and integration with other renewable energy sources. A perturb and observe (P&O) maximum power point tracking (MPPT) boost

converter is used to optimize power extraction from the photovoltaic (PV) array, ensuring it operates at its maximum power point under varying solar irradiance conditions. The P&O MPPT algorithm continuously adjusts the operating point by introducing small perturbations to the duty cycle of the DC-DC boost converter. This architecture ensures stable power distribution for EV fast charging stations, minimizing power losses and improving overall efficiency. The DC microgrid benefits from this configuration by achieving improved renewable energy utilization, reduced reliance on grid power, and enhanced power quality. The bidirectional energy flow capability allows for effective integration with battery storage systems, ensuring energy availability even during low solar generation periods. Implementing this solar P&O MPPT boost converter allows the DC microgrid to manage power distribution, support multiple EV chargers, and enhance sustainability by reducing carbon emissions through increased renewable energy penetration.

Single-Diode Solar PV Model: Designing a single-diode solar PV model involves analyzing the electrical characteristics of a photovoltaic (PV) cell. The single-diode model is one of the most commonly used to simulate the behavior of a PV cell. This model includes one diode, a current source, and series and shunt resistances to represent losses as shown in fig.5.

Fig. 2 solar PV P&O MPPT DC-DC boost converter

Basic Equation of the Single-Diode Model: The equation that governs the behavior of the single-diode PV model is derived from Kirchhoff's current law (KCL):

$$I = I_{ph} - I_D - I_{sh} \quad (1)$$

Where: I = output current of the PV module (A), I_{ph} = photocurrent, the current generated by light (A), I_D = diode current (A), I_{sh} = shunt current (A)

Fig. 3 equivalent model of PV solar.

1. Diode Current (I_D): The current through the diode is described by the Shockley diode equation:

$$I_D = I_0 \left(e^{\frac{V+I R_s}{n V_t}} - 1 \right) \quad (2)$$

Where: I_0 = reverse saturation current of the diode (A), V = voltage across the PV cell (V), R_s = series resistance (Ω), n = diode ideality factor (typically between 1 and 2), V_t = thermal voltage (V), given by $V_t = kT$

Here:

k = Boltzmann constant (1.38×10^{-23} J/K), T = temperature in Kelvin (K), q = electron charge (1.6×10^{-19} C)

2. Shunt Current (I_{sh}): The current through the shunt resistance R_{sh} is modeled as:

$$I_{sh} = \frac{V+I R_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (3)$$

3. Equation of the Single-Diode PV Model: By substituting the expressions for I_D and I_{sh} into the main current equation, we get the complete form of the single-diode model:

$$I = I_{ph} - I_0 \left(e^{\frac{V+I R_s}{n V_t}} - 1 \right) - \frac{V+I R_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (4)$$

4. Photocurrent I_{ph} : The current generated by the cell due to light is proportional to the incident light and is affected by temperature. It can be modeled as:

$$I_{ph} = [I_{ph,ref} + \mu I_{ph} \cdot (T - T_{ref})] \cdot \frac{G}{G_{ref}} \quad (5)$$

Where: $I_{ph,ref}$ = reference photocurrent at standard test conditions (STC), I_{ph} = temperature coefficient of photocurrent (A/ $^{\circ}$ C), T = cell temperature ($^{\circ}$ C), T_{ref} = reference temperature (usually 25° C), G = irradiance (W/m^2), G_{ref} = reference irradiance at STC ($1000 W/m^2$)

5. Saturation Current I_0 : The reverse saturation current varies exponentially with temperature:

$$I_0 = I_{0,ref} \left(\frac{T}{T_{ref}} \right)^3 e^{\frac{E_g}{n V_t} \left(\frac{1}{T_{ref}} - \frac{1}{T} \right)} \quad (6)$$

Where: $I_{0,ref}$ = reverse saturation current at reference temperature, E_g = bandgap energy of the semiconductor (typically 1.1 eV for silicon)

b. P&O MPPT Algorithm

The P&O MPPT algorithm adjusts the duty cycle (D) of the boost converter based on small perturbations to the PV voltage. The power change is determined as follows:

$$\Delta P = P(k) - P(k - 1) \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta V = V(k) - V(k - 1) \quad (8)$$

- if $\Delta P > 0$ and $\Delta V > 0$, increase V_{pv}
- if $\Delta P < 0$ and $\Delta V > 0$, decrease V_{pv}
- if $\Delta P > 0$ and $\Delta V < 0$, decrease V_{pv}
- if $\Delta P < 0$ and $\Delta V < 0$, increase V_{pv}

The updated duty cycle is calculated as:

$$D(k + 1) = D(k) + \alpha \cdot \text{sign}(\Delta P) \quad (10)$$

Where α is the step size for duty cycle adjustment.

Fig.4 flow chart for P&O MPPT algorithm

c. Boost Converter Design

The boost converter steps up the PV voltage to the required DC bus voltage. The output voltage of the boost converter is given by:

Fig.5 DC-DC unidirectional boost converter

$$V_o = \frac{V_{pv}}{1 - D} \quad (11)$$

Where: V_o = Output voltage of boost converter (V), V_{pv} = Input PV voltage (V), D = Duty cycle of the converter

The inductor value is selected to ensure continuous conduction mode (CCM) operation:

$$L = \frac{V_{pv}(1 - D)}{f_s \cdot \Delta I_L} \quad (12)$$

where: L = Inductor value (H), f_s = Switching frequency (Hz), ΔI_L = Inductor ripple current (A)

The output capacitor is designed to minimize voltage ripples:

$$C = \frac{I_o}{f_s \cdot \Delta V_o} \quad (13)$$

Where: C = Output capacitor (F), I_o = Output current (A), ΔV_o = Allowable voltage ripple (V)

4. CONTROL SCHEME

A. Designing for D-STATCOM shunt converter controller

A positive sequence estimator control based on an integrator is shown in Fig. 8 as a basic block. In this case, we use a pair of controls, namely MPPT and VSC. In order to extract the most power from the PV source, the MPPT control is used. When the grid voltages are distorted, there is an imbalance in the three-phase point of common interaction (PCI) voltages, voltage sag, or swell, the VSC control algorithm produces the gate pulses and enhances the PQ. The following components are included in the estimation: grid reference currents (GRC), net active component (wsp), PV feed-forward term (wpv), and loss component (wcp).

Fig.6 Block diagram of an integrator based positive sequence estimator control.

Fig. 7. Control scheme for shunt D-STATCOM converter

B. VSC Control

The figure of VSC control technique is depicted in Fig. 7. It shows adaptive dc-link voltage control and GRC. This scheme is explained as follows.

1) *Unit Templates Estimation*: The PCI line voltages (v_{sab} , v_{sbc}) are sensed, which are converted to the phase voltages (v_{sa} , v_{sb} , and v_{sc}) [21]. The phase voltages are then transformed to α - β -0 by applying Clark's transformation (CT) as depicted in Fig. 6

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_{s\alpha} \\ v_{s\beta} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{2}{3} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_{sa} \\ v_{sb} \\ v_{sc} \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

In order to reduce the amount of harmonics in these modified voltages, they are fed into a control system that uses an integrator and a positive sequence estimator. For optimal system functioning even in the most challenging situations (e.g., when grid voltages sag/swell, are unbalanced, distorted, or when there is a dc offset), an integrator-based positive sequence estimator control may extract PSCs from these imbalanced and distorted voltages. Here is how the PSCs are determined. The unbalanced three-phase voltages are converted into balanced components using the symmetrical components theory [22], [23] as

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_{p\alpha\beta} \\ v_{n\alpha\beta} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} J\omega_0 & \\ & -J\omega_0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_{p\alpha\beta} \\ v_{n\alpha\beta} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \omega_0 \\ \omega_0 \end{bmatrix} (v[k_\alpha \quad k_\beta] \begin{bmatrix} v_{p\alpha\beta} \\ v_{n\alpha\beta} \end{bmatrix}) \quad (15)$$

The above equation becomes

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_{p\alpha\beta} \\ v_{n\alpha\beta} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{[k_\alpha \quad k_\beta]\omega_0}{s^2 + 2[k_\alpha \quad k_\beta]\omega_0 + \omega_0^2} \begin{bmatrix} (s + J\omega_0) \\ (s - J\omega_0) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_{s\alpha} \\ v_{s\beta} \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

where $v_{p\alpha\beta}$ and $v_{n\alpha\beta}$ are PSCs and negative sequence components in α - β domain, k_α and k_β [22] are constants and ω_0 is the rated frequency ($2\pi \times 50 = 314$ rad/s). These PSCs are then converted in abc form. The PSCs (v_{pa} , v_{pb} , and v_{pc}) are extracted from this output by inverse CT

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_{pa} \\ v_{pb} \\ v_{pc} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{3}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{2}{3} & 0 \\ -\frac{1}{3} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ -\frac{1}{3} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_{p\alpha} \\ v_{p\beta} \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

These extracted positive sequence voltages (v_{pa} , v_{pb} , and v_{pc}) are used to estimate the in-phase unit templates (UTs) (u_{pa} , u_{pb} , and u_{pc}) as

$$V_t = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \times (v_{pa}^2 + v_{pb}^2 + v_{pc}^2)} \quad (18)$$

where V_t is terminal PCI voltage

$$u_{pa} = \frac{v_{pa}}{V_t}, u_{pb} = \frac{v_{pb}}{V_t}, u_{pc} = \frac{v_{pc}}{V_t} \quad (19)$$

2) *PI Controller for DC-Link Voltage*: For estimation of w_{cp} (loss component of dc-link), V^* dc (dc-link reference voltage) is deducted from sensed V_{dc} and an error is obtained, which is passed through a PI controller. It can be explained using the following equations as:

$$\omega_{cp} = \left(k_{pd} + \frac{k_{id}}{s}\right) \{V_{dc}^* - V_{dc}\} \quad (20)$$

where k_{pd} and k_{id} are the PI controller gains.

3) *DC-Link Voltage Adaptive Control*: The V_{dc} is adaptive flexibly in proportion to the variation in the grid voltages, to diminish the VSC losses. The V_{dc} depends upon the grid voltage. However, the energy generation by a solar PV system is independent of source voltage variation. It may be possible that during some dynamic conditions, the current may exceed the rating of the VSC. The V_{dc}^* is estimated as

$$V_{dc}^* = \lambda \sqrt{3} v_t \quad (21)$$

where value of λ is greater than one. Usually, λ is taken as 1.2.

4) *PV Source Component Computation*: The variations in PV irradiation create turbulences in the system. To compensate for it, a PV term is applied. This PV source term is applied to achieve efficient working of the present system in the dynamic conditions. It is calculated as

$$\omega_{pv} = \frac{2}{3} \times \frac{P_{pv}}{V_t} \quad (22)$$

5) *GRC Estimation*: For estimation of the gate signals of VSC, GRCs are estimated. These GRCs are computed as follows:

$$i_{sa}^* = \omega_{sp} \cdot u_{pa} \quad (23)$$

$$i_{sb}^* = \omega_{sp} \cdot u_{pb} \quad (24)$$

$$i_{sc}^* = \omega_{sp} \cdot u_{pc} \quad (23)$$

Here, ω_{sp} is the net weight component

$$\omega_{sp} = \omega_{cp} - \omega_{pv} \quad (24)$$

The differences between i_{sa}^* , i_{sb}^* , i_{sc}^* and i_{sa} , i_{sb} , i_{sc} are provided to the hysteresis controller, for VSC gate pulses generation.

B. Designing for series converter controller

The series converter is designed to enhance power quality in grid-connected systems by mitigating voltage disturbances such as sags, swells, and harmonics. As a key component of the Dynamic Voltage Restorer (DVR), the series converter operates by injecting compensating voltage into the grid to maintain a stable power supply for critical loads. The series converter adjusts its operation based on real-time voltage fluctuations at the Point of Common Coupling (PCC). It continuously

measures the grid voltage and injects the required compensating voltage using a predefined reference-based method. The system operates by directly sensing voltage variations and using pulse width modulation (PWM) techniques to regulate the injected voltage. The injected voltage is derived from real-time grid conditions, ensuring that voltage sags and swells are automatically corrected. To minimize harmonic distortion and maintain a sinusoidal voltage waveform, the series converter incorporates passive filtering techniques such as LC filters or transformer-based

isolation to smooth the injected voltage. As solar power generation varies, the series converter dynamically adjusts the compensating voltage based on the available power from the photovoltaic (PV) system. This ensures that the load receives a constant and stable voltage supply, regardless of fluctuations in the grid. By eliminating the need for complex control mechanisms, the proposed system simplifies operation while still achieving effective voltage regulation and harmonic suppression, ensuring high power quality in renewable energy-integrated grid systems.

Fig.8 Series converter controller

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Different Solar Irradiation variation on Grid Power Quality in D-STATCOM Mode

The simulation results demonstrate the impact of gradually increasing solar irradiation on power generation and grid power quality improvement in D-STATCOM operation as shown in Fig.10. Initially, at 0s to 0.2s, the solar irradiation remains at 0 W/m², meaning no solar power is generated, and the grid solely supplies the load. Between 0.2s and 0.4s, the irradiation increases from 0 to 300 W/m², leading to a gradual increase in solar power generation and a corresponding reduction in grid dependency. As a result, the D-STATCOM starts injecting reactive power, improving the voltage profile and reducing harmonic distortion. From 0.4s to 0.6s, the solar irradiation further rises to 500 W/m², enhancing power transfer to the grid and stabilizing the system voltage. During 0.6s to 0.8s, the irradiation increases to 800 W/m², allowing more active power injection into the grid, which further improves grid stability and power quality. Finally, between 0.8s and 1.0s, the irradiation reaches 1000 W/m², maximizing solar power generation and significantly improving grid voltage regulation. Throughout the simulation, as solar irradiation increases, the D-STATCOM effectively enhances power transfer to the grid, reduces voltage

fluctuations, and improves overall grid power quality, ensuring stable and efficient operation in renewable energy-integrated systems.

Fig. 9 simulation results for different solar irradiation variation

B. Voltage Compensation and Constant Load Supply Using DVR

The simulation results confirm that the series converter-based Dynamic Voltage Restorer (DVR), integrated with a Battery Energy Storage System (BESS), effectively maintains a constant power supply to the load by compensating for voltage disturbances in a grid-connected solar energy system as shown in Fig.11. During voltage sag between 0.2s and 0.4s, caused by sudden load variations, the DVR promptly injected the required compensating voltage using the BESS, ensuring that the load voltage remained stable and unaffected. Similarly, during a voltage swell between 0.6s and 0.8s, triggered by fluctuations in renewable energy generation, the DVR absorbed the excess voltage, preventing overvoltage stress on electrical equipment and maintaining the nominal voltage level. Throughout these disturbances, the DVR ensured that the load

received a constant and stable power supply, enhancing system reliability and power quality. The proposed system effectively mitigates voltage sags and swells, demonstrating its capability to support sensitive loads and maintain uninterrupted operation in solar-integrated power networks.

Fig. 10 Simulation results for during voltage sag and swell condition.

Fig.11 Grid current THD

5. CONCLUSION

The proposed hybrid system, integrating a solar power generation system with Dynamic Voltage Restorer (DVR) and D-STATCOM functionality, effectively addresses power quality challenges in grid-connected renewable energy networks. Through the use of a series converter-based DVR and Battery Energy Storage System (BESS), the system is capable of compensating for voltage sags, swells, and harmonics, maintaining a stable and constant supply to critical loads under fluctuating grid conditions. As demonstrated in the simulation, the system dynamically responds to variations in solar irradiance, with increased solar power generation improving grid power quality by reducing reliance on the conventional grid supply and ensuring stable voltage levels. The integration of the D-STATCOM function effectively mitigates reactive power imbalances, compensates for harmonics, and enhances voltage regulation. Furthermore, the BESS plays a crucial role in providing continuous voltage support during transient disturbances, ensuring the stability and resilience of the power supply. The results confirm that the system not only enhances grid stability but also improves power quality by reducing harmonic distortion and voltage fluctuations, thus making it a reliable solution for renewable energy-based grids. With the increasing integration of renewable energy sources like solar, this hybrid system provides a promising approach to achieving high-quality power supply while addressing the challenges posed by intermittent generation and load variability. The system's ability to compensate for grid disturbances and optimize power transfer makes it a suitable solution for future smart grids integrated with renewable energy.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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